

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: NDIFUNA****FIRST NAME: MOHAMMED****PROGRAM CODE: DCTD****COURSE CODE : ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did did not use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did did not use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: xx%

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401

Qn 1. Which of the following correctly explain the difference between Limitation and Delimitation as used in research?

- While limitation set the boundary, delimitation removes the boundary
- While limitations are the unexpected circumstances that constrain the interpretation of the dissertation research findings; the delimitations are anticipated limitations in interpreting the dissertation research results¹**
- While the imitations are factors within your control; delimitations are factors beyond your control as a researcher.
- None of these is correct

¹ James P Sampson, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research (Second Edition)*, Second Edition. (Tallahassee: Florida State University, 2017), 49 ,59.

Qn. 2. A researcher should avoid research questions

- If its answers would be merely speculative.
- If its answers require different capacities from the ones the researcher has.
- If its answers can't be plausibly disproved
- All the answers are correct²**

Qn.3. Which of the following statements relates to factorial validity?

- Concerns the congruence between what an instrument or test measures or is intended to measure
- Provides evidence that the content of the measure is congruent with the conceptual or theoretical basis of the instrument, test, questionnaire, structured interview, semi-structured interview, focus group, journal, written, visual, auditory, or tactile exercise, or observation³**
- Provides evidence that the measure's total, content, or factor-derived scale scores are associated with other measures of similar, or somewhat similar, constructs in a theoretically consistent direction;

² Kate Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, Ninth., vol. 45 (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2018), 27–28.

³ Sampson, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research (Second Edition)*, 41.

- Documents the evidence that clusters of empirically associated items can be identified and reproduced across norm groups in a manner consistent with the conceptual or theoretical basis of the measure

Qn.4. Which of the following is a factor to be considered when evaluating sources of information?

- Whether the source is published by a reputable press
- Whether the book or article is peer reviewed
- Whether the author is a reputable scholar
- All the above⁴**

Qn .5. Which forms of Chicago citation style are provided in Kate Turabian's Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations outlines?

- Parenthetical style and narrative style
- Author-date style and notes-bibliography style⁵**
- Source-date style and author-bibliography style
- Author-source style and notes-citation style

Qn. 6. Which of the following is the most correct statements a in respect of a research problem.

- They can be classified as either conceptual or practical problem

⁴ Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, 45:42.

⁵ Ibid., 45:144.

- The condition of a conceptual problem is a knowledge gap, and its cost is the consequence of a lack of knowledge
- The condition of a practical problem is any state of affairs that troubles the researcher or his readers
- All are correct**⁶

Qn.7. Identify the citation style documented in Kate Turabian's *Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*

- Harvard
- Chicago style**⁷
- American Psychological Association (APA) style
- Modern Language Association (MLA) style

Qn.8. Which of the following is not an issue to consider in the drafting of the final introduction should contain?

- The area of future research**⁸
- Opening context or background.

⁶ Ibid., 45:29.

⁷ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401 Coursepack*, Fourth Edition. (Bangui: Euclid University, 2021), 41.

⁸ Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, 45:111.

- A statement of your research question, or your research problem's condition.
- A statement of the significance of your question.

Qn. 9. Select the most correct answer in respect of paraphrasing

- Must be your words.
- The writing style you use to express the author's ideas must be different from the style the author used
- The information that you are providing must be an accurate representation of what the author originally wrote

All are correct⁹

Qn.10. A writer should not cite all the time. Under which of these three circumstances shouldn't the writer cite a source? Select all that are correct.

- When the information you are writing about is common knowledge that can be found in numerous areas, you do not need to cite its source
- When you have already cited the author many times and is unnecessary to cite again¹⁰**
- When ideas are similar to your own, and therefore are as good as your own
- When the idea is paraphrased and appears different

⁹ Cleenewerck and Gulma, *ACA-401 Coursepack*, 36.

¹⁰ Ibid.

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Cleenerwerck, Laurent, and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401 Coursepack*. Fourth Edition. Bangui: Euclid University, 2021.

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Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.